

Optimizing the deployment and use of new technologies in Search and Rescue: A recap from recent missions

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, four recent Search and Rescue (SAR) deployments of our team are briefly presented as baseline for contextualizing the challenge of designing the next generation of assets and tools for the field operations. Lack of preparedness, coordination and poor perimeter monitoring is, as expected, a major factor in large-scale disasters. Specific differences in task prioritization and speed are evident between small-scale events like train accidents and large-scale events like devastating earthquakes, leading to corresponding changes in the deployment or even the planning phases of a SAR mission. Citizens and especially spontaneous volunteers are important assets often overlooked. The “last mile gap” and changes in First Aid / medical response are also very critical factors that emerge more evidently as the scale of the disaster becomes larger. Finally, a few important guidelines and good practices are proposed for SAR-related R&D projects.

Keywords

Search and Rescue, First Responders, crisis management, emergency response, USAR, flash flood, wildfire.

INTRODUCTION

In Search and Rescue (SAR) operations, the First Responders (FR) are called upon to act in a very wide range of environments, conditions and limitations, associated to both external and internal factors. Weather, location, access, local infrastructure, travel time, are only some of these external factors, while team’s readiness level, organization, skill level and experience, toolkits available, are a few of the most important internal factors.

For Urban Search and Rescue (USAR) the most critical factor, besides FR safety, is speed. Every USAR mission is an effort against time, beginning as a speed race during the first few hours after the disaster event and gradually becoming a marathon run as the hotzone gets cleared in a more focused way. The FR teams must be capable both physically and mentally in adapting to this shifting working environment and every new challenge that emerges, keeping track of risks and possible hazards, while at the same time exploiting the probabilities of survival for the victims still trapped or undiscovered inside the disaster zone.

In this dynamic and challenging environment the FR teams need to be able to deploy and use every asset they have at their disposal in a timely and optimized way, such that maximizes the gain and the time spent with them. There are three main aspects that can group these assets, procedures and tools for the deployed FR team:

- **The FR team:** Personnel safety, situational awareness (low-level / personal), efficiency, endurance, cooperation, use of team-level assets (drones, cameras, sensors, communications, etc).
- **The victims:** Detection (sensing), triage / prioritization, medical assistance (first aid, stabilization), extrication / transfer.
- **The operations:** Situational awareness (Command, Control, Communication – C3), FR teams and

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assets tracking, worksite triage / prioritization, asset dispatching (e.g. UxVs, medevac), tactical communications (including specialized, e.g. inside rubble), logistics / support, infrastructure / provisions (field medical hubs, UCC/BoO), medium/long-term mission planning, etc.

Every one of these groups of assets, procedures and tools has its own internal organization, prioritization and standards, to a degree that depends mostly on the type of SAR mission, the scale of the deployment and the size of the FR team in the field. For example, INSARAG several aspects of a “standardized” USAR mission deployment, covering the entire five-phase workflow (Preparedness, Mobilization, Operations, Demobilization, Post-mission) with specific guidelines and documentation templates (INSARAG, 2020a; INSARAG, 2020b; INSARAG, 2020c). However, these guidelines do not address details and low-level decision making regarding how each asset and tool is used in the field, as this is the sole responsibility of each FR team. Similar guidelines and restrictions exist for other types of FR missions, like in firefighting, mountain or underwater SAR, etc.

Having optimized pre-defined plans on how each asset and tool can be used in the most effective way in a mission is of crucial importance, especially when the deployment is long-term, logistics and communications are stretched, or when the disaster is very extensive. Using these tools in a non-optimized way not only exhaust their availability and capacity (e.g. battery life) with limited results, but it may actually degrade the FR team’s effectiveness or even safety if unreliable information is not assessed as such (e.g. hazards undetected due to technological constraints).

Based on these observations, this paper aims at pointing out important aspects of properly planning, designing and developing SAR-related technologies for actual field deployment in real-world environments. In practice, the questions that need to be answered by any such new technology are:

1. *What does it bring to the FR team in the field as added value in operational level?*
2. *What are its benefits and constraints in the tactical / technical level?*
3. *How does it relate to existing practices and similar assets already in use?*
4. *What is the integration and training plan in order to be fully operational?*

The rest of this paper is organized as follows: In the following section, four real-world deployments of our team in 2023 are presented and briefly discussed as representative Use Cases of USAR-related issues described above. Next, the challenges encountered are discussed in the operational / mission-specific and non-operational aspects, as well as a summary of good practices identified during previous R&D projects developing such new technologies and tools. Finally, the recently initiated project SYNERGISE is presented as an example of such efforts to address some of these challenges and implement the lessons learned from past experiences.

BACKGROUND FROM FIELD DEPLOYMENTS

In the following sections four specific mission deployments of our team during 2023 are described briefly as Use Cases, mostly in the context of Urban Search and Rescue (USAR), although some of them included operating in suburban and rural environments. These provide the appropriate real-world frame of reference for discussing the technologies used, needs identified, as well as some guidelines in the mission planning and operational levels.

Use Case 1: Earthquake in Turkey-Syria

On the night of February 6th 2023, a 7.8R earthquake struck the southern-central regions of Turkey and northern-western regions of Syria (USGS, 2023). The epicenter was 37 km W-NW of the city of Gaziantep. The main event was followed by an additional 7.7R earthquake at noon, some 95 km away from the first epicenter, and several others of smaller magnitude in the next hours and days. The damage in the affected areas was widespread and devastating, with officially confirmed fatalities in the order of 60,000 (50,783 in Turkey and 8,476 in Syria) and injuries up to 122,000 people. The affected area was estimated to about 350,000 km², which is roughly the size of Germany, while the estimated number of people affected was 14 million people or 16% of Turkey’s population (UN, 2023).

Our team was deployed within the week shortly after the main event, comprising of a light USAR element including one K9 unit and all the necessary equipment. It operated under the directions and supervision of the Turkish authorities for about a week, mostly in the disaster zone of Adiyaman, a province in south-eastern Turkey. The deployment comprised mostly of ASR level 3 (INSARAG, 2020b) search in collapsed structures that had not been fully assessed previously due to lack of personnel, as well as some ASR level 4 (INSARAG, 2020b) works searching in identified locations with possibly live victims trapped inside rubble. The team was fully integrated in the general disaster response plan by LEMA and incorporated all the necessary INSARAG

reporting processes via VOSOCC, in close collaboration with LEMA and the other USAR teams. Close support was also ensured by the central C3 hub in Greece, supervising the entire mission and providing the necessary updates 24/7 via any communication means available in each specific location and time.

The scale and magnitude of the disaster was such that our USAR team could only assist in specific locations selected and prioritized by LEMA, hence limited work was performed in terms of worksite assessment and prioritization by our own team (i.e., prior to ASR level 3 operations).

Figure 1. Typical types of damages in residential areas in Turkey and Syria after the earthquake of Feb.2023 (Source: Al-Araby News, Daily Sabah, IANS News).

Use Case 2: Train Crash in Central Greece

On February 28th 2023, a head-on collision occurred at a rural location between the Greek towns of Tempi and Evangelismos in the Thessaly region in central Greece. The crash involved a passenger train (IC62) with 342 passengers and 10 railway staff and a freight train with 2 railway staff, totaling 354 people in both trains. The number of fatalities was tallied at 57, including the 2 from the freight train and 55 passengers and staff from the passenger train, most of them from the first wagon of the passenger train (closer to the crash). While criminal investigations are still in progress, all preliminary evidence shows that the accident happened because the passenger train was allowed to enter the wrong track and pass stopping signals, proceeding in the same track with the freight train coming from the opposite direction, due to lack of network supervision and automated emergency management systems (AlJazeera, 2023).

Our team was deployed immediately to the disaster zone, which was adjacent to the high-speed highway connecting northern and southern Greece in Thessaly. Hence, access to the location was relatively easy and fast, but approaching the crash site was severely hindered by extensive high-temperature fires, extensive debris field, dense smoke and low visibility due to night time, as well as risks of secondary explosions of possible flammable material in both trains (fuel, freight cargo, gas tanks in passengers' canteen wagon, etc).

After the first wide area assessment and rapid SAR performed during the night, our team was involved for several days in the disaster location assisting in secondary searches for casualties and forensic work, given the fact that verified and precise information about passengers and missing persons was severely delayed. Although the event itself was very contained in terms of both space and time, the field deployment lasted several days until conclusion.

Figure 2. The crash site after the train collision near the villages of Tempi / Evangelismos in central Greece in Feb.2023 (Source: Euronews, CNN Greece, Wall Street Journal).

Use Case 3: Wildfires in Greece

Starting from July and lasting throughout the end of August, several wildfire events were recorded and addressed in Greece during the summer of 2023. These included several islands in the Aegean Sea (Rhodes, Evia), Ionian Sea (Corfu), central and southern Attica region (Mt. Parnitha, Mt. Penteli) even inside the main urban grid of Athens (Saronida), as well as the largest and most long-lasting fire in Thrace (Alexandroupolis) which took almost three full weeks to extinguish. As a result, 28 fatalities and 75 injuries were officially recorded, as well as thousands of dead animals and at least 1,800,000 km² of burnt area, including 800 km² (2/3 of total) of the pine forests in Dadia, a natural habitat and protected region (Wikipedia, 2023).

Our team assisted the deployed elements of the Fire Service in almost all these locations, mostly as secondary units and less as fire fighting elements due to our teams' specialty and expertise (SAR, medevac). Due to the extreme weather conditions in many of these events, i.e., very strong dry winds and prolonged air temperatures up to 42-45 °C, there was constant need for medical assistance and evacuations for the local populations and tourists (high season). In several cases the evacuation required transferring people via boats, when this was the only safe route to escort out of the hazard zones. In other cases, medical assistance and evacuation was even more challenging, when there was no clear fire front inside the urban grid (Athens) and strong winds created new fire seeds along its path inside residential areas, with limited visual reference due to heavy smoke and night time.

The severe fire period lasted for two full months (July-August) and required long-term standby, provisions, rotation schedules and alternative mobilization plans the team. This is particularly difficult to ensure and sustain when the distances to the deployment locations are further and further away from the central C3 and Base of Operations (BoO).

Figure 3. Satellite post-assessment of damage caused by wildfires in Rhodes, Attica and Thrace during the summer of 2023 in Greece (Source: Copernicus EMS / EU).

Use Case 4: Floods in Central Greece

On the week of September 4th-9th 2023 heavy rainfall throughout Greece has caused several overflows in dams and escape routes in the agricultural belt of Thessaly region. As a result, severe flooding has occurred in villages and suburban areas in that region, totaling to about 700 km² of land and drowning tens of thousands of livestock animals. The harsh weather conditions were part of the “Daniel” storm that passed through Greece. A total of 15 fatalities were recorded and hundreds of cases of infections were reported to hospitals in the following days, due to waste, dead animals and bacterial infections in the stagnant waters (EUMETSAT 2023; EFAS 2023).

Typically, the event was not characterized as flash flood, as it evolved throughout a period of 24-48 hours in total, depending on the exact area and severity. Nevertheless, during the first few hours there was immediate need for evacuations in many villages, since the rising water was endangering access routes and safe escape if delayed.

Our teams’ deployment in the region included two phases: First, during the event and the few hours after its peak, performing SAR operations focused on possible trapped or injured victims. Second, in the following days, locating and assisting in the evacuation isolated groups of people, providing essentials (such as food, water, medications, etc), draining flooded buildings, restoring access to flooded areas.

Figure 4. The village of Metamorfofi near Karditsa in central Greece, prior and after the floods in Sept.2023 (Source: National Observatory of Athens – NOA / meteo.gr)

CHALLENGES IDENTIFIED

There are two categories of challenges identified in developing and deploying new SAR-related technologies. Specifically, the operational aspect, dealing with the mission specific issues related to real-world deployment in the context of SAR, and the non-operational aspect, associated to the planning and development phases of these new tools, mostly associated to corresponding R&D projects that produced them.

This section briefly discusses each of these categories, drawing outcomes and lessons from the Use Cases presented previously, as well as experiences from R&D works where our team was involved during the last few years for developing such SAR-related technologies.

Operational and Mission-Specific Issues

Lack of Coordination and Perimeter Monitoring

One of the most evident and common factor throughout the disaster events in UC1-UC4, as well as the general experience from other USAR deployments in the past, is the lack of coordination and centralized C3 during the first few hours after the main event. This becomes more and more relevant, evident and long-lasting as the scale of the event is larger. In UC2 (train crash) where the hotzone and scattering of debris was relatively constrained, this lack of coordination was evident for a few hours, mostly due to the conditions (night, intense fire, dense smoke) rather than the extent of damage. In contrast, in UC1 (Turkey) or UC3 (wildfires) the affected areas were in the order of tens or even hundreds of km and the deployed SAR teams faced severe difficulties in assessing the situation or even coordinating with each other in the field.

In some cases where the disaster zone spans in entire regions, as in UC1 in Turkey, the USAR teams face additional challenges that include perimeter security and protection from possible looting, as both the worksite and Base of Operations (BoO) locations are very difficult to monitor 24/7 under these conditions. It is very common to have numerous civilians, relatives and neighbors of the possibly trapped victims underneath a collapsed building, moving around the worksite all the time trying to assist, while at the same time a USAR team is trying to follow proper procedures, ensure FR safety and deploy the technological assets according to guidelines for optimal performance while this is unfeasible (e.g. geophones).

Operational Shifts in Focus and Use of Assets

Even in more area-constrained and properly monitored disaster areas as in UC2 (train crash), the deployment of widely used technologies has not been fully studied and assessed. For example, in that specific context the more or less “standardized” approach of launching a few Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAV) to make a quick area assessment was not compatible to the situation at hand: Night time and dense smoke made RGB/NV visuals severely degraded in quality and use, similar to the thermal/IR/NIR due to the intense fires at the crash site. In addition, the relatively small scale of the disaster area meant that the UAV deployment time is directly comparable to the assessment performed by actual FRs moving into the area on foot immediately. Of course, there are other benefits of deploying UAVs in such a scenario, such as placing overview cameras via aerial monitoring or having communication relays directly above debris, but this entails a different deployment plan, prioritization and execution upon arrival at the scene – and possibly a different set of devices attached on the UAV even before that.

Experience shows that there are distinct differences between small-scale and large-scale events, in relation to their space and time they span. In the first case, as in UC2, the main focus of the FR teams is shifted towards the rapid SAR, i.e., keeping the mobility and “momentum” high when searching for victims that may be detected and recovered immediately away from the hazards (fires, explosions, smoke, toxic gas, etc). In terms of INSARAG, this is mostly associated with ASR levels 2-3 operations. On the other hand, in the case of large-scale damage in extended areas, precision and sustainability of operations becomes more relevant, e.g. overlapping technological assets with FRs or K9 units in order to attain higher reliability in possible victim detections. In terms of INSARAG, this is mostly associated with ASR level 3-4 operations. However, even assets that have already been widely used and evaluated in SAR conditions, like UAVs for worksite mapping, do not adhere specific “standardized” procedures and specifications w.r.t. their deployment, but rather depend solely on the experience that each FR team has gained from previous missions.

For large-scale, long-term SAR deployments as in UC1, the aspect of logistics and support from the organization’s central C3 becomes extremely important. Due to the extent of damage, the (expected) lack of coordination locally, as well as the extensive preparations required simply to get into the affected areas

(transportation, paperwork, provisions, etc), create a different set of challenges and critical aspects that need to be addressed. This is operational too, but at the broader sense of FR team deployment, rather than problems, risks and hazards that the team faces at the worksites. Consequently, having reliable, long-range and omniscient communication assets available on-demand at all times, between the deployed FR team and the central C3 back home maybe thousands of km away, is of paramount importance. Practical things like provisions and shift rotations are handled locally, but long-term sustainability of the mission as well as safe infil/exfil of the team from the disaster zone requires significant support from the home base.

Citizens as Sensing Resources

There are also some important aspects to discuss specifically for flooding events like in UC4 (Thessaly). A few years back the notion of “Citizen Observatories” (CO) was introduced within the context of EU-funded R&D projects, aiming at the “Citizen Science” idea and the prospect of turning every citizen into an asset for such endeavors. More specifically, in the context of Civil Protection and SAR-related operations, CO could be used to provide thousands of citizens with the ability to monitor and send visual or other measurement / sensing data to a back-end platform, which could perform data fusion, correlation and updates of corresponding hazard mappings like for flooding. This idea was investigated in previous EU-funded R&D projects with very interesting results (SCENT, 2019) and it is almost certain that, if they were implemented properly and preemptively, the effects of the floods in UC4 could be significantly mitigated or avoided altogether. Having very recent or perhaps real-time information about blockages, damaged drainage routes, changes in land use, as well as water levels and damages while the event is still in full progress, is perhaps the most important asset for both the central planning and coordination by the Civil Protection, as well as for the SAR deployment and the FR teams that enter the disaster zones in a safe and efficient manner.

Process Improvement via Post-Mission Assessment

Experience shows that the phase of post-mission assessment is of paramount importance for every SAR organization that needs to retain a high level of readiness and effectiveness. This assessment includes at least three main aspects: (a) **the FR team**, (b) **the assets and tools**, and (c) **the operations and procedures**. For (a) the FR team, the assessment is related to personal evaluation and possible aspects that may require special attention, for example Psychological First Aid (PFA) for preventing possible PTSD-related issues. For (b) the assets and tools, they need to be assessed and evaluated in terms of true added value, quality of control and accuracy of result throughout their deployment during the mission. These factors may change compared to their initial installment due to wear, improper use by the operators or simply by incompatibilities with the actual situation at hand, as in the case of UAVs mentioned previously for UC2. Regarding (c) the operations and procedures, these need to be continuously re-assessed and re-evaluated for any changes required either by changes in the operational context (change of missions) or in the FR team itself (change of skills). In terms of process improvement, this is the baseline for any quality control system that is designed and implemented in numerous other areas of expertise and engineering (CMU, 1996).

Spontaneous Volunteers

Although often neglected from the central disaster response planning by the Civil Protection, the local volunteers outside any formal structure or organization are extremely important resource. They provide immediate assistance to victims even before the FR teams arrive; they provide relevant and timely information about the affected areas, possible victim count and location, available access routes; and in the short- and long-term recovery phase, they provide assistance to the affected population, as they are often part of. The lack of centralized structure and specific legislation governing their activities are major hindering factors for including them more formally by central authorities neither in planning or operational context; nevertheless, there is significant effort during the last few years in bringing their capabilities and needs into focus, in order to make use of their availability and efforts.

The “Last Mile Gap”

As much as the lack of coordination locally, another aspect of every disaster event while it is evolving and right after that is the “gap” between the emergency response and the affected population. This usually spans up to 6-24 hours or even more after the main event, depending on the scale of the disaster zone and the extent of damages in infrastructure. It includes not only the physical barriers in reaching the affected people and trapped victims, but also the information gap that unfolds as the communication infrastructure is saturated locally,

severely limited due to damages or completely destroyed. It is not uncommon in the first six hours to have humanitarian provisions (food, water, medicine) close to an affected area and the response teams having no way to know where exactly to target inside the disaster zone for delivery or how to get there, while at the same time the affected population not knowing that help is coming or where exactly it will be delivered. This is another aspect that SAR-related technologies need to address more intensely, with reliable, resilient and publicly accessible communications for everyone, instead focusing exclusively on FR-oriented solutions.

Changes in First Aid Operations

In large-scale disaster events like in UC1 some of the standard procedures and protocols are revisited and adjusted based on the environment and the situation at hand. This includes not only the USAR operations according to INSARAG as mentioned above, but also the medical emergency response and everything that is related to victim treatment. The typical medevac procedures after victim detection dictate stabilization, extrication and transfer to the closest appropriate hospital via any means available for safety and speed. The experience from UC1 shows that this approach may not be feasible in such situations: The medevac assets are too few, the ground access routes are blocked or with detours of extreme delays, the hospitals and central medical hubs are out of reach or saturated by the large number of victims. Therefore, the approach that may be more feasible and life-saving given these conditions may be to have field hospitals of capacity as extensive as possible (including field surgery, if needed) very close to the locations of increased inflow of victims, instead of the standard medevac expected in almost any other situation. This is still a debatable subject, as it is extremely hard to assess the true effectiveness of each option, i.e., medevac at all costs or local treatment, but it should be in the scope and planning of emergency response for large-scale disaster events, as much as for relevant new technologies and tools (e.g. automated victim triage tracking).

Areas of Need for New SAR Technologies

Given the experiences, observations and limitations described above, mostly based on UC1-UC4, gaps and areas for technological improvement emerge in relation to how SAR operations may be supported:

- FR safety at the personal level (gear, wearables, localization, biometrics).
- Team safety via hazard mapping, coordination, monitoring.
- Area assessment, marking, dynamic mapping, movement coverage (especially indoors).
- Fast automated visual screening of images, videos, maps (for victims and hazards).
- Remote sensing via multiple modalities (visual, chemical, sound, seismic, etc).
- Remotely operated or fully autonomous robots, putting distance between FRs and the scene.
- Automated access routing and navigation for the FR team.
- Mini-robotics & soft-robotics, used for specific tasks (e.g. search shafts).
- Victim detection, localization, access discovery, medical assessment.
- Indoor positioning & tactical communications (intra-team and team-C3).
- Augmented situational awareness for the FR team via VR/AR tools.

It should also be mentioned that the assets and tools used by the FRs may be used or reconfigured in a way not initially intended by the developer, if it makes sense operationally for addressing a specific problem at hand. For example, it is not uncommon for FR teams to use simple devices like a typical smartwatch with a cardiac pulse sensor (HR indicator) on a victim as an additional tool during secondary assessment / monitoring or a similar GPS-enabled gadget as geolocation “tagging” for a victim that may move, e.g. sink deeper inside debris or drift away during a flood. This means that adaptability, modularity and interoperability of any such new SAR-related technology are as important as the core functionality intended by design.

Non-Operational Limitations and Good Practices

Besides the core issues related to the operational aspects of mission planning and field deployment of FR teams, there are several other aspects in developing new technologies that work as hindering factors and counter-productively, usually very early on while in design or prototyping phases. The experience from DRS cluster projects within the general context of EU Horizon H2020 has revealed their importance and relevance:

- Usually there is limited or no provision budget-wise for full IPR protection of the developed technologies. The technical partners are often reluctant to fully disclose previous work or implement some novel design knowing that it cannot be protected in terms of IPR, especially after 2-3 years from its conclusion (e.g. no funding for patents).

- The expected Technology Readiness Level (TRL) expected for these new technologies is usually at 4-5 for most of them at the end of each R&D project (RIA/IA). This means that, even when fully successful, the corresponding prototypes are only a demonstration and the result of a feasibility study, instead of tools that are almost ready for commercialization and field deployment. In most cases, this final stage requires 1-4 additional years of work, depending on the entry-level and exit-level maturity of each developed technology.
- Standardization and interoperability of these new tools has to be completed or at least progressed towards its final stages, before they can be fully integrated in the current toolbox and assets of operational SAR organizations. Furthermore, this process has to demonstrate that the new tools are fully compatible and actually entail specific added value to the existing standards and protocols that the SAR organization is trained upon and implements in the field (e.g. INSARAG guidelines for USAR).
- The FR market for presenting and commercializing these new technologies is relatively small, is the cost or capabilities are more relevant to international rather than national team capacities and disaster response missions. Even internationally, there is only a handful of large SAR organizations capable of purchasing new tools at the very early stage, i.e., with expectancy of high cost and for large-scale deployment.

Despite these hindering factors and limitations that work as barriers in developing new innovative tools for the FR teams in the field, there are a few useful conclusions from experiences in such R&D projects:

1. **Early end-user involvement:** Perhaps the most critical factor in developing successful FR technologies is involving these organizations in the process from day one. Instead of having the end-users defining top-level requirements and constraints at the beginning and then later on testing the almost-finished products, there are very important advantages and gains in including them throughout the entire development process, using their feedback continuously.
2. **Expectation management:** It is certain that some of the top-level requirements from the end-users will not be fully met in the final products, especially when the expected outcome is at the level of TRL 4-5. Similarly, some of the constraints that are considered mandatory in real-world FR field deployments will be stretched or somehow violated at some degree, since the context here is trials instead of real missions. Similarly, some technological aspects and preconditions may have to be revisited, reshaped or completely changed, due to the unique nature of SAR environment of operations (e.g. unreliable network connectivity, power supply, etc). The goal should be to find a common ground between the sets of expectations from both sides, end-users and engineers, so that the final product is something that points to the right direction for both.
3. **Extensive field trials:** One of the unique aspects of working with SAR end-users is that, in order to better understand and integrate the new tools, the entire development process has to be designed from the start as fully iterative and closely adapted to the actual deployment environment, i.e., the field operations. There is a large gap to cover between FRs and technology partners, from one side towards novel technologies that they have probably never used before and from the other side towards transforming the lab tests into field trials for their tools.

Based on these limitations and good practices, empirically discovered and evaluated during such R&D projects, we now have a specific and valuable set of guidelines on how to plan, manage and implement them in practice. Furthermore, it is important to make sure that everyone understands the true value of the end result, which is producing life-saving assets for SAR organizations, perhaps some years into the future.

THE SYNERGISE PROJECT

It is impossible to address every FR requirement and technology gap within the scope of a single R&D project. The context of the problem at hand, i.e., SAR operations, as well as the individual challenges emerging in different types of missions and environments create a wide range of tasks to analyze and develop appropriate solutions.

The SYNERGISE project is different in that sense, compared to previous R&D project for SAR-related technologies. Instead of focusing exclusively on the requirements on specific types of SAR missions or of individual FR organizations in their consortiums, it draws seeds and aggregated conclusions from the FR background, previous R&D works, as well as recent progress in SAR technologies that is either already in use or identified by several actors as important to have. This material is summarized by the International Forum to Advance First Responder Innovation (IFAFRI) as a guideline of ten common global capability gaps, technically described by FR organizations around the world (IFAFRI, 2023).

In SYNERGISE these technological gaps are addressed by developing an integrated toolkit for improved management of natural and man-made disasters, which includes:

- UxVs swarm consisting of aerial, legged and snake-like robots for autonomous area assessment and victims detection.
- Wearables for real-time monitoring of FR biometrics, gas/environmental sensing for potential toxics and explosives detection.
- Advanced localization systems for indoor and outdoor operations.
- Augmented reality (AR) for remote control and rich map visualization for FRs.
- AI-enabled information fusion for improved decision-making.
- Rapidly deployable tactical communications for robust data exchange.
- An interoperable Incident Management System (IMS) for C3 operations.

These innovative solutions and new tools will equip FR teams with capabilities and assets that will: (a) improve situational awareness both indoors and outdoors, personally and also collaboratively as a team, (b) reliable localization, tracking and biometrics monitoring of FRs, (c) boost the Common Operational Picture (COP) capabilities via rich sensing and AI-enabled data fusion, (d) provide interoperable and compatible tools for FRs according to their real-world operational needs.

The project extends previous experience and integrates the practices of involving end-user organizations very early on in the development process, in order to have continuous evaluation and feedback. Furthermore, it implements a plan of extensive field trials throughout its timeline, not only in the full pilots but also in multiple small-scale events, where the technologies and prototypes under development will be tested, evaluated and validated.

The SYNERGISE started officially on September 2023 and it will evolve in a period of 42 months.

CONCLUSION

In this paper, several Use Cases from recent SAR missions were briefly presented and discussed, as baseline for contextualizing the needs of FR teams operating in the disaster zones, as well as the technological gaps that have been identified as such throughout these deployments. It is expected that the identification of FR needs from real-world operations, as well as global technology gaps in the context of SAR missions or various types, can enable to better address these in current and future R&D projects for the next generation of assets and tools.

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